

Participatory metagenomics in the project “Microbial Childhood: Restor(y)ing Daycare Ecologies”

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These science activities were developed in a one-year multidisciplinary research project focusing on microbes in a Finnish daycare. The project was titled [Microbial Childhood: Restor\(y\)ing Daycare Ecologies](#), funded by Maj and Tor Nessling Foundation and led by Professor [Zsuzsa Millei](#) at Tampere University, Finland.

Although microbes compose our bodies and are ubiquitous in everyday life, they are not easily accessible given that they cannot be seen without technological aids. To develop a project that would encourage children to attend to microbes, two social scientists, two artists and two ecologists collaborated with the daycare. The project involved 4 to 6-year-old children, although younger children also participated in some activities. In designing the research, we combined the method of **participatory metagenomics** (Greenhough, Dwyer, Grenyer, Hodgetts, McLeod & Lorimer, 2018) with artistic practices focusing on the senses and interoception. Our idea was that participatory metagenomics would bring natural scientific knowledge about microbes to the children, whereas artistic practices would allow them to relate with microbes in more sensory and experiential terms (see also Kervinen et al., 2024). The science activities described below composed the participatory metagenomics part of the project.

Participatory metagenomics

Metagenomics is an analysis method where DNA sequencing is used to determine the composition of the focal organismal group in a sample, in effect producing information about the bacterial species present in the environment where the sample is taken from. In this study, we targeted bacteria and analysed samples taken from a daycare and its surroundings. Metagenomics becomes *participatory* when it is the participants who choose the sampling locations and the results are used as a starting point for further reflection (Greenhough et al., 2018). In our version, it was up to the children to choose where to take the samples. This part of the project began in October with some introductory activities, where we used books and explanations to learn about what microbes are and observed how microbes grow on petri dishes.

The ecologists, Mira Grönroos and Laura Soininen, then helped the children take samples from their desired objects and places in the daycare. The children chose, among others, Legos, the floor, toilet seat and butter. The samples then went through

ordinary DNA extraction, sequencing and bioinformatic steps in a similar manner as in Soininen et al. (2024) and Grönroos et al. (2024). The entire process took approximately five months. During this time, the ecologist and her colleagues edited educational videos documenting the samples' journey through the laboratory so that the children could follow what happens during the wait for the results.

In April, when all the sample processing steps were done, the Mira Grönroos visited the children twice to discuss the results. She had prepared an information sheet for each of the 11 samples, which were used in both sessions. Included in the sheet was a picture of the object sampled, a dot representation of the number of different bacteria (i.e. genus level diversity) found in the sample, a bar chart showing abundance ratios (at phylum level), and example pictures of species belonging to the most abundant groups. The sheets were used for discussions.

The following detailed notes of the participatory metagenomics in the daycare are replicable in other settings.

The ecologist researcher, Mira Grönroos, visited children altogether four times. At the first visit, she discussed with the children what microbes are, how tiny they are and about the variety of places they live in (Fig. 1). Then she asked children to find some object that they wanted to research to find out if there were microbes in it. Children selected a variety of objects, such as grass, toy, finger and sofa cushion. Then the researcher provided petri dishes with bacterial culture medium gel. Each child pressed an object of their choice onto the gel or first swabbed the object (e.g. sofa) with a wetted cottonwool stick and then swabbed the gel. Researcher closed the petri dishes firmly with tape and placed them in zipper bags.

Figure 1. An example of one of the three figures the researcher showed the children at the first visit. This figure illustrates the size and amount of microbes showing that if their hair would be as wide as three stored building, a coli bacterium would be a size of a one-liter juice can, single staphylococcus bacterium a size of a potato and a bacteriophage a size of one grain of rice. Right side of the figure illustrates that in a spoonful of soil there is approximately as many microbes as there are people on earth. Illustration is created using BioRender by Mira Grönroos.

After one week, the researcher had video-meeting with the kids. She showed how the cultures looked like (Fig. 2), discussed about the growth and, also asked the children to think where they would like to take the next samples.

Figure 2. On the left, the researcher uses black cardboard as a background for one of the cultures and shows it to the children via video connection. On the right, one example of the bacterial cultures, here is what was grown from sofa cushion. Pictures taken by Veera Pukkila and Mira Grönroos.

After another one week, the researcher visited children for the second time. She discussed about the culturing results and introduced the idea of DNA. Then children were again let to select their desired sampling object which was either swabbed or placed in a zipper bag as such. Children selected objects such as Legos, floor, toilet seat and butter (Fig. 3.). Some additional samples were taken based on personnels' interests (e.g. stair railing) or researcher's interests (e.g. apple).

Figure 3. Example of the objects children decided to take DNA samples. On the upper row there are examples of successful samples (from left to right: Legos, grass, stick and crispbread) and on the lower row there are examples of samples that did not yield enough DNA to be sequenced (toilet seat, leaves, stone and climbing wall). Pictures taken by Mira Grönroos.

Researcher took the DNA samples to laboratory, and they went through ordinary DNA extraction, sequencing and bioinformatic steps in a similar manner as in Soininen et al. (2024). Many of the samples did not produce enough DNA to be sequenced due to very varying sample matrices and small sample sizes (e.g. the area swabbed by the child). Altogether 11 samples produced enough DNA and were subsequently sequenced. We took videos of most of the laboratory phases and edited altogether six short educational videos. During the following six- and half-month period, these videos were shown to the children to demonstrate microbial study methods and the phases that children's samples went through before getting the results.

In the videos, the main concepts discussed in the preceding face-to-face meetings, such as DNA, were briefly recapped (Fig. 4.). The topics of each video was: 1) weighting samples and breaking cell walls with microscopic beads, 2) extracting DNA i.e. removing unwanted substances through several steps including e.g. pipetting liquids that precipitate or dilute the substances and centrifuging through microscopic filter that allows separation based on molecule size, 3) verifying success of DNA extraction using gel electrophoresis in which electric current carries fluorescently labeled DNA molecules in a gel, 4) multiplying DNA using polymerase chain reaction, 5) transferring samples to sequencing lab to read the DNA code and 6) bioinformatic work at computer to process DNA data and compare DNA code with databases to identify bacterial composition of the samples.

Figure 4. Pictures showing examples of the videos. First row from left to right: 1) The researcher explains bringing the samples to the lab technician/analyst, 2) animation of how a bead tube breaks the cell walls, 3) the output of a centrifuge, 4) laboratory analyst pipetting narrated by the researcher, and second row, 5) the lab mascot revives attention, 6) using PCR machine to multiply DNA, 7) using a plant book as a tangible example of a taxonomic reference and 8) an illustrative animation how DNA code (illustrated by colored bars) is used to identify bacterial composition of the samples (uppermost row shows an imaginary sample and the rows below show the imaginary database the given sample is compared with). Pictures and videos produced and taken by Mira Grönroos and Laura Soininen.

To consider the attention span of the children the videos were kept brief: the length of the videos varied between 2–8 minutes. The researcher, already familiar to the children, hosted all the videos. Other persons appearing in the videos was laboratory analyst, bioinformatician and a red-eared slider, laboratory’s mascot turtle. We tried to maintain children’s interest, for example, by asking questions and using a familiar speaking style. To keep the videos understandable, we used age-appropriate narration and demonstrative illustration. For example, we used a plant book as a tangible example of species identification and an illustrative animation to give an idea how the sequenced DNA code is compared with bacterial databases.

Finally, when all the sample processing steps were done, the researcher visited the children twice to present and discuss the results. The third visit begun with a short recap of what was done and what cells and DNA are. A figure assembled from Legos served as an example of a

multicellular organism and a single piece of a unicellular organism (Fig. 5.). The researcher had prepared an A4-sized picture of each of the 11 samples. These included a picture of the object sampled, the number of different bacteria (i.e. genus level diversity) found in the given sample using as dots, and a bar chart roughly showing abundance ratios (at phylum level). Of the most abundant groups (i.e. phyla), an example picture of one species belonging to the given group, was included. The researcher went through all the samples with the children and told some small detail about each sample that she thought could be interesting for the children. For example, that the most abundant genus in a sample was *Lactococcus*, which is used, for instance, to make cheese or that in another sample, there was bacteria potentially capable to break down gasoline.

Figure 5. On the left, the Lego figures used to illustrate multi- and unicellularity and on the right, an example of one of the result pages that was printed in A4-size and presented and discussed with children. Translations: “Swabbed sample from Legos” (title) and “Altogether 300 bacterial genera” (below). Photo credits: Mira Grönroos and Wikimedia Commons (NIAIS; CDC/Dr. V. R. Dowell, Jr. (PHIL #2965), 1972; Doc. RNDr. Josef Reischig, CSc; US gov; Aslam Z., Lee C. S., Kim K.-H., Im W.-T., Ten L. N., Lee S.-T.).

At the fourth and final visit, the researcher concentrated more on diversity issues. She had run an ordination analysis (non-metric dimensional scaling) for those 11 samples and based on that, she marked the sample names in tapes on the floor and asked each child to select a spot (Fig. 6.). She gave sample descriptions presented at the previous visit to each child and then discussed of each sample. The purpose of this was to illustrate the differences among samples: which samples were similar, i.e. close to each other, such as bun and crispbread, and which samples were very different from each other, i.e. far apart, such as apple and Legos.

Figure 5. On the left, non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) ordination of the samples taken by the children, and on the right, how this configuration was prepared on the floor for the children. Pictures produced and taken by Mira Grönroos.

At each face-to-face visit, the researcher spent approximately 20 minutes with a group of 10 children at the time. Due to illnesses, some children missed some of the visits.

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